

THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353770>

The problem of human trafficking and related crimes is acute for the world community. The belief that the slave trade and slavery are over forever is a thing of the past. Today, it is indisputable that the activities of criminal organizations engaged in this criminal trade are becoming more active. According to international organizations, the profit of traffickers is approximately \$150 billion per year. In terms of scale and profitability, this activity is second only to the arms and drug trade. At the same time, there is evidence that criminal groups increasingly prefer this type of criminal business. It follows from official sources that more than 2.5 million people become victims of human trafficking every year. 80% of the victims are women, up to 50% are minors¹. The main purpose of human trafficking is the sexual exploitation of women and minors.

According to UN statistics, 600-800 thousand women and men are taken abroad fraudulently, their share is 80 percent of human trafficking crimes².

The transnational nature of human trafficking is of particular concern. State borders are not an obstacle for criminals. On the contrary, criminal organizations skillfully take advantage of the difference in legal systems, different levels of economic development and income of the population.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of public security and combating crime to a qualitatively new level» №-6196 dated March 26, 2021, a mechanism of holistic management and continuous control based on the republic—region—district—mahalla system, ensuring peace was introduced and stability in the country through effective coordination of activities to ensure public security of internal affairs bodies and other state bodies³.

As stated in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan UP-5005 dated April 10, 2017 «On measures to radically improve the efficiency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, strengthen their responsibility for ensuring

¹ <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2019/07/30/human-trafficking/>

² Рустамов М. Адвокатское бюро «Konstant-Mas» // Адвокат. – 2017. – № 4. – Б. 26

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of public safety and combating crime to a qualitatively new level" №.-6196 dated 03/23/2021 (<https://lex.uz/docs/5344121>)

public order, reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens», existing threats and dangers, in particular, international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, the spread of ideas alien to our people among young people and its strengthening poses new tasks for law enforcement agencies to prevent and eliminate them in a timely manner⁴.

Today, international organizations have adopted a number of documents aimed at combating human trafficking on a global scale. A universal definition of human trafficking, slavery, institutions and customs similar to it has been developed. Nevertheless, the problem of introducing international legal structures into national legislative systems is currently very relevant.

Over the years of independence, comprehensive measures have been taken in the country to prevent crime and combat crime, positive results have been achieved in maintaining law and order in the country and the criminogenic situation has significantly improved.

We consider it our primary task to improve the functioning of all parts of the education system in accordance with modern requirements.

It should be noted that in the context of rapid reforms in Uzbekistan, it is not uncommon for some people to take to the streets of criminals. It is also natural that such crimes cover more of the economic sphere in the process of forming socio-economic relations.

In connection with the implementation of large-scale reforms in the country, the system of preventive services and their activities have been radically reorganized. As a result of the reforms, firstly, the organizational structure, the main directions and tasks of preventive services were revised, secondly, law enforcement bases were created in all regions of the country where the activities of prevention inspectors were created, thirdly, the interaction of sectoral law enforcement services was improved, and fourthly, material and technical the basis and material incentives and social and legal protection of preventive services, fifth, the system of provision, retraining and advanced training of law enforcement officers, in particular, prevention inspectors.

⁴ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the efficiency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, strengthen their responsibility for ensuring public order, reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens" No.-5005 dated 10.04.2017 (<https://lex.uz/>).

As a logical continuation of the ongoing reforms in the judicial system, especially in the system of internal affairs, in order to more firmly ensure the protection of the recognized highest value of a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable human rights, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Internal Affairs bodies» entitled «General Provisions» was adopted on September 16, 2016. its goals, main objectives, main areas of activity, the basic principles of law enforcement, as well as the duties of law enforcement officers to comply with the requirements of the law, cooperation with other law enforcement agencies and organizations, scientific achievements, modern technologies. the norms regulating the use of information systems are included. One of the main tasks of the state is to ensure security in our society, maintain peace and tranquility of the population, protect the freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, that is, life, health, honor and dignity of property from various forms of aggression.

In fulfilling these tasks, law enforcement agencies have a special role as a system of large-scale and multifaceted activities to protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, maintain public order and security, as well as crime prevention. Therefore, since the first days of independence, along with the judicial system in the republic, radical reforms have been carried out in the branch services of law enforcement agencies that ensure law and order in society.

Based on the above, the social danger of human trafficking for society is that they cause material, moral and physical damage to citizens. In addition, criminals commit the crime of human trafficking and profit illegally. These funds allow them to live a free life. In this regard, law enforcement officers, in particular prevention inspectors, must tirelessly fight against any forms of these crimes.

Literature:

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